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Controlled Strain Resonance Frequency Fatigue Test Bench for CFRP

Eduard Relea, Varun K. Urundolil, Christian Baerthaler, Lukas Weiss, Konrad Wegener
inspire AG & ETH Zürich

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High-speed stamping presses

- High-speed stamping presses, like the BRUDERER BSTA, need to keep up with increasing customer demands regarding an increase of both quality and quantity of the delivered parts. Being among the quickest presses currently present on the market, these BSTA presses can reach speeds up to 2000 strokes per minute (spm) with a stroke of 8 mm, while guaranteeing a lifetime of 20000 hours at such speeds.
- New requirements were defined: a 25% increase of the stamping speed, up to 2500 spm, while maintaining the same stroke of 8 mm.
- The cast iron ram of a BRUDERER BSTA-200 was redesigned in CFRP.
- Due to the stamping force of 200 kN and the impact nature of the stamping process, high strains take place into the material.

Source: Bruderer

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CFRP Fatigue

- Stamping presses are expected to function for at least 1 billion cycles between maintenance intervals → expected great fatigue behavior of the employed materials.
- Newly developed controlled strain resonance frequency fatigue test bench → forced vibration of a 2 mass oscillator.
- The testing occurred at the specimen's resonance frequency with a constant and controlled strain of 0.1%.
- The tested specimens are cylindrical, and the arrangement of the fibers was unidirectional (UD) – 0° and 90°.

Test bench

- Acoustically insulated box
- Cooling
- Counter horn
- Air bearing
- CFRP Probe
- Eddy current sensors
- Horn
- Piezo actuator
- Eddy current sensor amplifier
- Mineral cast base

LabVIEW code

CompactRIO system → controller with processor

Eddy current sensor signal converter

Piezo Amplifier

Ram: cast iron vs. CFRP

